

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10927478>
UDC 533.2

ON LOADING THE NEIGHBORHOOD OF A CUT IN A LINEAR ELASTIC PLANE BY A PAIR OF FORCES

Dinh Tien Dung, Van Thi Kim Xuyen,
Faculty of Basic Science,
Ho Chi Minh City University of Transport,
Ho Chi Minh City

Annotation: The formulation of the problem of loading a cutout in a linearly elastic plane by a pair of forces is considered. Based on the obtained system of boundary integral equations, a discrete solution method is proposed, and the results obtained are presented.

Keywords: linearly elastic plane, system of boundary integral equations, fracture mechanics, stress-strain state, discrete solution

О НАГРУЗКЕ ОКРЕСТНОСТИ РАЗРЕЗА В ЛИНЕЙНОЙ УПРУГОЙ ПЛОСКОСТИ ПАРУ СИЛ

Динь Тьен Зунг, Ван Тхи Ким Сюен,
факультет фундаментальных наук,
Хошиминский университет транспорта,
г. Хошимин

Аннотация: Рассмотрена постановка задачи о нагружении выреза в линейно упругой плоскости парой сил. На основе полученной системы граничных интегральных уравнений предложен дискретный метод решения и представлены полученные результаты.

Ключевые слова: линейно-упругая плоскость, система граничных интегральных уравнений, механика разрушения, напряженно-деформированное состояние, дискретное решение

1. Introduction

Quasi-brittle fracture mechanics, based on the concepts of a linear elastic body, considers the asymptotic distribution of the stress-strain state near the load-free crack edge. The crack in this case is modeled by a mathematical cut and the general solution depends on three real parameters, which are present as factors in the asymptotic terms. Another model representation of a crack-like defect is a physical section. The scale level of this section determines the approach to describing the destruction process. If this is a crystal lattice level [5, 6], then the process in this case is described by interatomic interaction potentials. An alternative approach is to choose a scale level where the continuum mechanics hypotheses remain valid [7]. An assessment of this level is given in works [1, 2]. To date, the most studied and experimentally substantiated is the limiting state of a crack of the normal rupture type. In this case, the problem of destruction can be considered both through the application of concentrated forces to the shores of a mathematical section and a physical one. However, rotating the corresponding forces ninety degrees in one direction for a physical cut will result in a pair of forces. This work is devoted to consideration of the corresponding effect for a linearly elastic medium.

2. Formulation of the problem

Let us consider loading the vicinity of the notch with an interaction layer equal in thickness [1, 2] in a linear elastic plane according to the scheme, corresponding to plane shear type failure.

We believe that the relationship between stresses and strains is described by the relations of the linear theory of elasticity for the case of plane deformation. Due to the antisymmetry of the external load relative to the plane $x_1 = 0$, we consider the upper half-plane ($x_1 \geq \delta_0/2$) (Fig. 1), and replace the action of the layer with the load on the half-plane $\hat{q}(x) = -(\hat{\sigma}_{11}\vec{\theta}_1 + \hat{\sigma}_{21}\vec{\theta}_2)$ (hereinafter $x \equiv x_2/\delta_0$ – dimensionless coordinate; $\hat{\sigma}_{ij} = \sigma_{ij}\beta$ i, $j = 1,2$ – dimensionless stresses; $\beta = \frac{2(1-\nu^2)}{\pi E}$ – material parameter; E – elastic modulus; ν – Poisson's ratio).

Figure 1 – Upper half-plane ($x_1 \geq 0/2$)

Flamant's relations [4] relate the external load $\hat{q}(x)$ with boundary displacements by the dimensionless expression

$$\hat{u}_2(x) = -\hat{P} \ln\left(\frac{x+a}{L+a}\right) + \int_0^L \hat{\sigma}_{21}(\xi) \ln\frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi} d\xi, \quad (1)$$

$$\hat{u}_1(x) = \int_0^L \hat{\sigma}_{11}(\xi) \ln\frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi} d\xi. \quad (2)$$

here $\hat{u}_i(x) = \hat{u}_i(x_1, x)|_{x_1=\delta_1} = \frac{u_i(x)}{\delta_0}$, $i = \overline{1,2}$ are dimensionless

displacements of the upper boundary her half-plane; $\hat{P} = P\beta/\delta_0$ – dimensionless force per unit thickness; L – remote point with zero displacement; L – distance from the origin to L .

Stress is related to strain by Hooke's law in a plane strain state

$$\varepsilon_{11} = \hat{A}\hat{\sigma}_{11} - \hat{B}\hat{\sigma}_{22}, \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_{21} = \hat{C}\hat{\sigma}_{21}, \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{A} = \frac{(1-\nu^2)}{E\beta} = \frac{\pi}{2}$

$$\hat{B} = \frac{\frac{\nu(1+\nu)}{E}}{\beta} = \frac{\nu\pi}{2(1-\nu)};$$

$\hat{C} = \frac{2(1+\nu)}{E\beta} = \frac{\pi}{(1-\nu)}$ are dimensionless constants.

In further presentation, we will assume that the displacement $\hat{u}_2(x_1, x)$ in the interaction layer is determined by the following expression

$$\hat{u}_2(x_1, x) = \frac{\partial \hat{u}_2(x_1, x)}{\partial x_1} \Big|_{x_1=0} x_1. \quad (5)$$

Let us consider the deformation of the material of the interaction layer

$$\varepsilon_{21} = 0.5 \left(\frac{\partial \hat{u}_1(x_1, x)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \hat{u}_2(x_1, x)}{\partial x_1} \right)$$

From equality (5) it follows that

$$\left. \frac{\partial \hat{u}_2(x_1, x)}{\partial x_1} \right|_{x_1=0} = 2\hat{u}_2(x_1, x)|_{x_1=\delta_0/2} = 2\hat{u}_2(x). \tag{6}$$

From (4), (6) we obtain

$$\hat{u}_2 = \hat{C} \hat{\sigma}_{21} - 0.5 \frac{\partial \hat{u}_1}{\partial x}. \tag{7}$$

Transform (1) using (7)

$$\hat{C} \hat{\sigma}_{21}(x) - 0.5 \frac{\partial \hat{u}_1(x)}{\partial x} = -\hat{P} \ln \left(\frac{x+a}{L+a} \right) + \int_0^1 \hat{\sigma}_{21}(\xi) \ln \frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi} d\xi. \tag{8}$$

Let us differentiate with respect to x the left and right sides of equality (2)

$$\frac{d\hat{u}_1}{dx} = \int_0^L \hat{\sigma}_{11}(\xi) \frac{1}{(x-\xi)} d\xi. \tag{9}$$

We assume that during the application of an external load, according to the diagram in Fig. 1, the antisymmetry condition for the stress tensor component σ_{11} is satisfied. Consequently, on the middle plane of the interaction layer $x_1 = 0$ we have

$$\sigma_{11}(x_1, x)|_{x_1=0} = 0. \tag{10}$$

From the equilibrium conditions of layer $\frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{11}}{\partial x_1} = -\frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{21}}{\partial x}$, assuming the law of change of σ_{11} along the x_1 coordinate to be linear, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{11}(x_1, x)}{\partial x_1} = 2(\hat{\sigma}_{11}(\delta_0/2, x) - \hat{\sigma}_{11}(0, x)) = 2\hat{\sigma}_{11}(\delta_0/2, x).$$

Taking into account condition (10), the connection between the components of the stress tensor at the layer boundary takes the form

$$\hat{\sigma}_{11}|_{x_1=\delta_0/2} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{21}}{\partial x} \Big|_{x_1=\delta_0/2}. \tag{11}$$

The equilibrium equation of the layer of the form $\frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{22}}{\partial x} = -\frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{21}}{\partial x_1}$ with connection (4) will take the form

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{22}}{\partial x} = -\frac{1}{\hat{C}} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{21}}{\partial x_1} = -0.5 \frac{1}{\hat{C}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{\partial \hat{u}_1(x_1, x)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \hat{u}_2(x_1, x)}{\partial x_1} \right). \tag{12}$$

From expressions (6) and (12) it follows

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{22}}{\partial x} = -\frac{1}{2\hat{C}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{\partial \hat{u}_1(x_1, x)}{\partial x} \right) = -\frac{1}{2\hat{C}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial \hat{u}_1(x_1, x)}{\partial x_1} \right) = -\frac{1}{2\hat{C}} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{11}}{\partial x}. \tag{13}$$

Taking into account the decay of the displacement field at infinity and law (3), expression (13) gives the following relationship between the diagonal components of the stress tensor $\hat{\sigma}_{22} = -\frac{1}{2\hat{C}} (\hat{A}\hat{\sigma}_{11} - \hat{B}\hat{\sigma}_{22})$ or

$$\hat{\sigma}_{22} = -\frac{(1-\nu)\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{4(1-0.25\nu)}. \tag{14}$$

Thus, we have a system of integral equations (8), (9), supplemented by connections (11) and (14). Let us rewrite the resulting system of integro-differential equations

$$\hat{C}\hat{\sigma}_{21}(x) - 0.5 \frac{\partial \hat{u}_1(x)}{\partial x} = -\hat{P} \ln \left(\frac{x+a}{L+a} \right) + \int_0^L \hat{\sigma}_{21}(\xi) \ln \frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi} d\xi, \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{d\hat{u}_1}{dx} = \int_0^L \sigma_{11}(\xi) \frac{1}{(x-\xi)} d\xi, \quad (16)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_{11}|_{x_1=\delta_0/2} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{21}}{\partial x} \Big|_{x_1=\delta_0/2}, \quad (17)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_{22} = -\frac{(1-\nu)\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{4(1-0.25\nu)}. \quad (18)$$

Substituting (16) into (15), system (15) – (18) is transformed to the form

$$\hat{C}\hat{\sigma}_{21}(x) - 0.5 \int_0^L \hat{\sigma}_{11}(\xi) \frac{1}{(x-\xi)} d\xi = -\hat{P} \ln \left(\frac{x+a}{L+a} \right) + \int_0^L \hat{\sigma}_{21}(\xi) \ln \frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi} d\xi, \quad (19)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_{11}|_{x_1=\delta_0/2} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{21}}{\partial x} \Big|_{x_1=\delta_0/2}, \quad (20)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_{22} = -\frac{(1-\nu)\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{4(1-0.25\nu)} \quad (21)$$

with the boundary condition $\sigma_{21}|_{x=0} = 0$. Here the main unknowns are the boundary stresses σ_{11} and σ_{21} .

3. Discrete representation of the solution

Let us divide part of the half-plane boundary ($x > 0$) into n unit elements. We assume constant stress within the length of each δ_0 -element. In this case, the generalized stresses in the i – th element on the segment $i-1 \leq x \leq i$ are determined by the expressions $\sigma_{11}^{(a)} = \int_{i-1}^i \hat{\sigma}_{11}(x) dx$; $\sigma_{21}^{(i)} = \int_{i-1}^i \hat{\sigma}_{21}(x) dx$.

Let us construct discrete expressions of integral operators in equations (19), (20). Consider the operators

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \int_0^L \hat{\sigma}_{21}(\xi) \ln \frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi} d\xi = \int_0^n \hat{\sigma}_{21} \ln \frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi} d\xi = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{i-1}^i \hat{\sigma}_{21} \ln \frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi} d\xi = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_{21}^{(i)} \left[\int_{i-1}^i \ln |x-\xi| d\xi - \int_{i-1}^i \ln(L-\xi) d\xi \right] = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \psi^{(i)}(x) \sigma_{21}^{(i)} - \sum_{i=1}^n C^{(i)} \sigma_{21}^{(i)}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\psi^{(i)}(x) = \int_{i-1}^i \ln|x - \xi| d\xi, C^{(i)} = \int_{i-1}^i \ln|L - \xi| d\xi, A_2 = \int_0^L \hat{\sigma}_{11}(\xi) \frac{1}{x-\xi} d\xi = \int_0^n \hat{\sigma}_{11} \frac{1}{x-\xi} d\xi = \sum_{i=1}^n \psi_1^{(i)}(x) \sigma_{11}^{(i)}, \psi_i^{(i)}(x) = \int_{i-1}^i \frac{1}{x-\xi} d\xi.$

After passing to discrete operators, we integrate the left and right sides of the system under consideration over the j segment, where $j - 1 \leq x \leq j$.

As a result, operator A_1 takes the form

$$A_1^j \left[\sigma_{21}^{(i)} \right] = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_{21}^{(i)} \int_{j-1}^j \int_{i-1}^i \ln|x - \xi| d\xi dx - \sigma_{21}^{(i)} \int_{j-1}^j \int_{i-1}^i \ln|L - \xi| d\xi dx,$$

and operator A_2 accordingly $A_2^j \left[\sigma_{11}^{(i)} \right] = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_{11}^{(i)} \int_{j-1}^j \int_{i-1}^i \frac{1}{x-\xi} d\xi dx.$

Let us introduce the notation

$$\phi^{(ji)} = \int_{j-1}^j \int_{i-1}^i \ln|x - \xi| d\xi dx, \psi_1^{(ji)} = \int_{j-1}^j \int_{i-1}^i \frac{1}{(x-\xi)} d\xi dx; C^{(ji)} = \int_{j-1}^j \int_{i-1}^i \ln(L - \xi) d\xi dx,$$

and give the final expressions for them.

In the case $j > i$

$$\phi_{(+)}^{(ji)} = -(j-i)^2 \ln(j-i) + \frac{1}{2}(j-i-1)^2 \ln(j-i-1) + \frac{1}{2}(j-i+1)^2 \ln(j-i+1) - \frac{3}{2},$$

$$\psi_{(+)}^{(ji)} = -2(j-i) \ln(j-i) + (j-i-1) \ln(j-i-1) + (j-i+1) \ln(j-i+1).$$

When $j = i$ to calculate the integral $\int_{j-1}^j \int_{j-1}^j \ln|x - \xi| d\xi dx, x \in [j-1; j]$

let's present it in the following form $\int_{j=1}^j \left[\int_{j-1}^x \ln(x - \xi) d\xi + \int_x^j \ln(\xi - x) d\xi \right] dx.$

After performing the integration, we get $\phi_{(0)}^{(ji)} = -\frac{3}{2}$

For $\psi_1^{(ji)}$ in the case $j = i$ we have: $\psi_1^{(ji)} = 0.$

Case $j < i: \phi_{(-)}^{(ji)} = (i-j)^2 \ln(i-j) - \frac{1}{2}(i-j+1)^2 \ln(i-j+1) - \frac{1}{2}(i-j-1)^2 \ln(i-j-1) - \frac{1}{2},$

$$\psi_{(-)}^{(ji)} = 2(i-j) \ln(i-j) - (i-j-1) \ln(j-i-1) - (i-j+1) \ln(i-j+1).$$

For $\forall i, j$

$$C^{(ij)} = -(n-i)\ln(n-i) + (n-i+1)\ln(n-i+1) - 1,$$

$$D^{(j)} = \int_{j-1}^j \ln\left(\frac{x+a}{L+a}\right) dx = (j+a)\ln\frac{j+a}{n+a} - (j+a-1)\ln\left(\frac{j+a-1}{n+a}\right) - 1.$$

Taking into account the constancy of stresses on the segment $[j-1, j]$ from (20) we obtain $\sigma_{21}^{(j)} - \sigma_{21}^{(j-1)} = -2\sigma_{11}^{(j)}$.

As a result, the complete discrete model, due to the introduced notations, will take the form:

$$\hat{C}\hat{\sigma}_{21}^{(j)} - 0.5A_2^j [\sigma_{11}^{(i)}] = -\hat{P}D^{(j)} + A_1^j [\sigma_{21}^{(i)}], \quad (22)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_{12}^{(j)} - \hat{\sigma}_{12}^{(j-1)} = -2\hat{\sigma}_{11}^{(j)}, \quad (23)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_{22}^{(j)} = -\frac{(1-\nu)\hat{\sigma}_{11}^{(j)}}{4(1-0.25\nu)}. \quad (24)$$

The proposed discretization of the system of integro-differential equations (19) – (21) is close in ideology to the boundary element method [3] with a constant approximation of the stress field on the element. However, in this case, the stresses are constant on each element (over its entire length), and are not calculated at a specific (mid) point of the element with subsequent constant propagation throughout the entire element.

Bibliography

- [1] Glagolev V.V. About one method of determining the connections between the critical values of the characteristics of the process of steady-state separation of material / V.V. Glagolev, A.A. Markin // Problems of Strength. – 2006. No. 2. 47-58 p.
- [2] Glagolev V.V. Estimation of the thickness of the interaction layer as a universal material parameter / V.V. Glagolev, A.A. Markin // News of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Mechanics of solids. – 2006. No. 5. 194-203 p.
- [3] Crouch S. Boundary element methods in solid body mechanics / S. Crouch, A. Starfield: Per. With. English – M.: Mir, 1987. 328 p.
- [4] Lurie A.I. Theory of elasticity / A.I. Lurie. – M.: Nauka, 1970. 939 p.
- [5] Novozhilov V.V. On the necessary and sufficient criterion of brittle strength / V.V. Novozhilov //PMM. – 1969. No. 2. 212-222 p.
- [6] Petrov Yu.V. On the “quantum” nature of destruction of brittle media / Yu.V. Petrov // Dokl. AN. – 1991. T. 321. No. 1. 66-68 p.

[7] Cherepanov G.P. Self-destruction / G.P. Cherepanov // Problems of mechanics of deformable solids and rocks. Collection of articles for the 75th anniversary of E. I. Shemyakin. – M.: FIZMATLIT, 2006. 142-152 p.

Список литературы (перевод)

[1] Глаголев В.В. Об одном методе определения связей между критическими значениями характеристик процесса установившегося разделения материала / В.В. Глаголев, А.А. Маркин // Проблемы силы. – 2006. № 2. 47-58 с.

[2] Глаголев В.В. Оценка толщины слоя взаимодействия как универсального параметра материала / В.В. Глаголев, А.А. Маркин // Известия Российской академии наук. Механика твердого тела. – 2006. № 5. 194-203 с.

[3] Крауч С. Методы граничных элементов в механике твердого тела / С. Крауч, А. Старфилд; Пер. С. англ. – М.: Мир, 1987. 328 с.

[4] Лурье А.И. Теория упругости / А.И. Лурье. – М.: Наука, 1970. 939 с.

[5] Новожилов В.В. О необходимом и достаточном критерии хрупкой прочности / В.В. Новожилов // ПММ. – 1969. № 2. 212-222 с.

[6] Петров Ю.В. О «квантовой» природе разрушения хрупких сред / Ю.В. Петров // Докл. АН. – 1991. Т. 321. № 1. 66-68 с.

[7] Черепанов Г.П. Самоуничтожение / Г.П. Черепанов // Проблемы механики деформируемого твердого тела и горных пород. Сборник статей к 75-летию Е. И. Шемякина. – М.: ФИЗМАТЛИТ, 2006. 142-152 с.

© *Dinh Tien Dung, Van Thi Kim Xuyen, 2024*

Поступила в редакцию 01.02.2024

Принята к публикации 16.02.2024

Для цитирования:

Dinh Tien Dung, Van Thi Kim Xuyen On loading the neighborhood of a cut in a linear elastic plane by a pair of forces // Инновационные научные исследования. 2024. № 2-1(39). С. 13-20. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>